

PalArch's Journal of Archaeology
of Egypt / Egyptology

**APPLICATION OF ICT IN THE AREA OF VIRTUAL
ARCHAEOLOGY FOR STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL
EDUCATIONAL NEEDS IN THE STAGE OF
COMPULSORY SECONDARY EDUCATION**

J. Durga Prasad Rao^{*}, Hari Shankar Prasad Tonde^{}, Prachi Sharma^{***}**

^{*} Phd. Computer Science, Additional Director and HOD Computer Science, Shri Shankaracharya Mahavidyalaya, Junwani, Bhilai, CG. j.durga.prasad.rao@gmail.com

^{**} Assistant Professor, Department of Computer Science (UTD), Sant Gahira Guru University, Sarguja Ambikapur, CG. hari.1978.rakhi@gmail.com

^{***} Phd. Education, Assistant Professor, Pt. Harishankar Shukla College, Raipur, CG. prachihsc95@gmail.com

**J. Durga Prasad Rao, Hari Shankar Prasad Tonde, Prachi Sharma,
Application of ICT in the area of Virtual Archaeology for students with special
educational needs in the stage of Compulsory Secondary Education-Palarch's Journal
Of Archaeology Of Egypt/Egyptology 17(7),ISSN 1567-214x**

Abstract

Today's culture is persuaded that quality schooling must enter all young people, beyond exemption. In this context, particular focus is put on the variety of students in the ESO. Adequate preparation can contribute to greater personal and social growth, such that students will transition into an increasingly challenging society. Modern Information and Networking Systems promote teaching-learning cycles in this sense. A few of them, Archeology Virtual, allows it possible to turn heritage artifacts into real and powerful instruments at the disposal of the school and, ultimately, of society.

Keywords:

ICT, VIRTUAL ARCHAEOLOGY, ANCE, ULD.

1. Introduction

Attention to diversity is laid out as a guiding precept that can guide all primary education, with the goal of presenting all students with the knowledge that is suitable to their characteristics and needs.

In this sense, the following legal framework is established, which will be the regarding when planning our work:

1. Organic Law of Education, 2/2006, May 3.
2. RD 1631/2006, December 29, which regulates the teachings high school minimums.
3. RESOLUTION of February 10, 2005, by which agrees to the publication of the Student Attention Plan Foreigner and Minorities (BOCYL of March 11).
4. DECREE 52/2007, of May 17, ESO curriculum of Castile and Leon.
5. ORDER EDU / 693/2006, of April 25, which regulates the plans to promote reading and the development of reading comprehension of the educational centers of Education High school.
6. ORDER EDU 1952/2007, of November 29, by which Assessment is regulated in Compulsory Secondary Education in Castilla y León.
7. RESOLUTION of March 28, 2007, of the Management General of Professional Training and Educational Innovation, by which the publication of the Customer Service Plan is agreed students with Special Educational Needs.
8. ORDER EDU / 865/2009, of April 16, by which regulates the evaluation of students with educational needs special schools enrolled in the second cycle of Education Infant and in the stages of Primary, Secondary Education Compulsory and accalaureate, in Castilla y León.
9. RESOLUTION of August 17, 2009, of the DGPOIE, which regulates the design, application, monitoring and assessment of significant curricular adaptations to students with special educational needs enrolled in the second cycle of Early Childhood Education and the stages of Primary Education, Secondary Education Compulsory and Baccalaureate in the Community of Castilla y Lion.

10. ORDER EDU / 1152/2010, of August 3, by which regulates the educational response to students in need specific educational support in the second Cycle of Early Childhood Education, Primary Education, Education Compulsory Secondary, Baccalaureate and Education Special Education, in the educational centers of the Community of Castilla y León.
11. ORDER of February 14, 1996 regulating the procedure for conducting the assessment psychopedagogical and the opinion of schooling and establish the schooling criteria for students with Special educational needs.

2. The challenges of today's school

The purpose of Education is to ensure that students acquire study, work and effort habits, in addition to some minimum knowledge, which allows them to enter the labor market, training them to exercise their rights and obligations in life.

The achievement of all this translates into objectives and competencies that the student must achieve at the end of the stage compulsory basic training.

Today's society has the conviction that it is necessary improve the quality of education, but also that this benefit must reach all young people, without exclusions. A good education is the greatest wealth and the main resource of a country and its citizens.

Currently, cultural and linguistic diversity are defining elements of the new European societies, for this when forming the school we must have very present this diversity of students and the need to reach the totality, without excluding any of them. As a result, we must all work together, teachers and organisations, to build a new, creative, multicultural school that reacts to the needs of people, with the aid of the fundamentals of their community and preparation that encourages them to practice their rights and responsibilities as people. It is therefore necessary to encourage sufficient learning, allowing all students to grow more individually and socially, in order to be able to incorporate into society.

Within this context, more attention should be paid, if possible, in students with special educational needs (ACNEE), understanding by such, that type of student that requires during a period of their schooling, certain supports or specific actions and which is thus recognized in the corresponding Psychopedagogical Assessment report and Opinion of Schooling, if applicable, or Compensation Educational.

Figure 1 Typology of ACNEE students

"guide" teacher who helps to achieve the objectives raised at the beginning of the course. These can be specified in the following sections:

1. Attend and respect the diversity of interests, abilities and motivations of the students, especially those with Special educational needs.
2. Guarantee adapted, inclusive and quality teaching that respond to the educational needs of our students due to their different capacity conditions, learning style, motivation, interests, differences cultural and socioeconomic, in accordance with the principle of equal opportunities.
3. Provide students with an appropriate educational response and quality that allows you to achieve the greatest development personal and social in order that they can be integrated into the society in a balanced way but with a critical spirit and ability to change.

3. Students with educational needs specials: ACNEE

In Compulsory Secondary Education, special emphasis is placed in the attention to the diversity of the students. The purpose of this stage consists of ensuring that students acquire the elements.

4. Students with compensation needs educational: ANCE

Inclusive Education is an educational movement supported by UNESCO, within the School for All (EFA) program, which aims to end the exclusion of any student. It is here where students with compensation needs education (ANCE) have the possibility of finding an answer to their needs, since at all times of their learning they will start from premises such as diversity, not exclusion, equality before education and where the teaching work will be carried out from dimensions of presence, participation, progress, which are key elements of the inclusive school.

There are different types of ANCE students, which should to consider:

The objective to be achieved is to guarantee care education and promote the school integration of students with the characteristics described, promoting the development of capacities included in the general objectives of the stage and make possible, where appropriate, their incorporation into a program of Social Guarantee or Initial Professional Qualification or a Curriculum Diversification program.

Future is Universal Design Learning (UDL). It can define UDD as a planning and design strategy for products and environments aimed at achieving a society inclusive, that ensures full equality and participation of all people.

Such a strategy is based on the following principles regarding multiple media:

Figure 2 Typology of ANCE Students

4. Presence of ICT in the classroom through Virtual Archeology

New Knowledge and Communication Technology are required to promote teaching-learning processes and provide a platform also for transformation of a culture of self-learning, re-learning, innovation and imagination in the educational environment. In this way, the use of ICT is applied to an innovation process that diversifies the environments and possibilities for learning, which, in turn, contributes to promoting better learning opportunities.

It is within the framework of an inclusive, innovative and modern school, where ICT have a place. Within this broad field of technologies, for the teaching and knowledge of Heritage and History, it is worth highlighting the advantages of using Archeology Virtual which allow us to travel in space and time without move from the classroom, becoming an attractive tool, different and playful, which makes learning easier and nice.

To teach the subject we will use multimedia resources from Archeology, such as Balawat, Classical Culture, Roman Villa de la Olmeda, etc.

The following figures illustrate various examples of activities to carry out in the classroom, with ANCE students.

6. The Universal Learning Design

ICTs, of great value in the current educational system, have not yet brought about the fundamental changes desired for the majority of students with special educational needs.

The technologies that are currently serving as catalysts for these new ideas. The one that seems to have the best future is Universal Design Learning (DUA). It can define UDD as a planning and design strategy for products and environments aimed at achieving a society inclusive, ensuring full equality and participation of all people.

Such a strategy is based on the following principles regarding multiple media:

Figure 3 Balawat.com Main Screen

Figure 4 DVD cover of Achilles on the island of Skyros

1. Representation, to give students various forms of acquiring information and knowledge.

2. Of expression, to offer students alternatives to show what they know.

3. Commitment, to take advantage of the interests of students and motivate them to learn.

These principles can be specified in providing options for:

1. The pursuit of interests.
2. Maintaining effort and persistence.
3. Self-regulation.

Figure 5. Virtual image of the Roman baths of San Juan de Maliaño

Figure 6 Visit to a virtual Roman house

All of this would contribute to the development of a new education, collaborative and collective, with a creative and versatile approach, with efficient, realistic teacher preparation, with methods for community engagement and participation in the learning process, creating positive and constructive partnerships between teacher and management structures.

Figure 7 Roman Villa of Olmeda

7. CONCLUSIONS

Plan and sustain processes of innovation and school improvement. To overcome barriers, it is a basic principle in today's school.

These technologies have been reaching all areas of knowledge. Thus, with Archeology it has resulted a new discipline: Virtual Archeology, which enables make heritage assets authentic and powerful resources at the service of the school.

This communication shows how the use of Archeology Virtual facilitates understanding and greater interest in the knowledge of History, especially considering that is focused on students with compensation needs educational, by allowing them to find answers to their peculiarities, thereby favoring the creation of a school inclusive.

Finally, it is proposed to create as a starting point, a Universal Design Learning (DUA) scenario, which provide multiple means of engagement, motivation and participation, to facilitate the knowledge of students with learning difficulties.

Figure 8 The Universal Learning Design

Bibliographic references

ARNAIZ, P. (2003): "Inclusive education: A school for all". Cistern. Malaga.

COLL, C. (2007): "A crossroads for school education", in Cuadernos de pedagogía , nº 370, pp. 19-23.

ECHEITA, G. (2006): "Education for inclusion or education without exclusions" . Narcea. Madrid.

FULLAN, M. (2002): "The new meanings of educational change". Octahedron. Barcelona.

MONTOLÍO, R. and CERVELLERA, L. (2008): "A school of all people for all people", in Electronic Magazine

Iberoamericana on Quality, Efficacy and Change in Education. 6, pp. 100-119.

ONRUBIA, J. (2004): "Psychopedagogical criteria and resources to attend to diversity in secondary school" . Graó. Barcelona.

ORTIZ, M. and LOBATO, X. (2003): "Inclusive school and school culture: some empirical evidence", in. Bordón, nº 55, pp. 27-39.

PUJOLAS, P. (2001): "Attention to diversity and cooperative learning in compulsory education". Cistern. Malaga.

Internet references

<http://www.villaromanalaolmeda.com> [Consultation: 24-Nov-2020]

<http://www.balawat.com> [Consultation: 24-Nov-2020]

<http://www.culturaclasica.com/> [Consultation: 24-Nov-2020]

<http://www.unesco.org/new/en/education/themes/leading-the-international-agenda/education-for-all/> [Consultation: 24-Nov-2020]

http://www.unesco.org/education/pdf/SALAMA_S.PDF
[Consultation: 24-Nov-2020]

portal.uam.es/portal/page/profesor/epd2_asignaturas/asig14648/informacion_academica/Guia%20par [Consultation: 24-Nov-2020]